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Influence of Artificial Intelligence Technology on Teaching Slow Learners

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Abstract

Despite the fact that artificial intelligence (AI) and education could appear like a futuristic innovation, they are already part of our lives and educational institutions. We can simplify both the lives of students and instructors by using AI education. AI education allows all students to acquire a high-quality education and customizes learning. Although every student's learning style is unique, generally they are divided into three categories based on learning: Passive learners, Slow learners, Quick Learners. The main goal of this work is to determine how artificial intelligence affects teaching for slow learners and also provided different AI methods to teach slow learners.

Keywords:Artificial Intelligence, Influence, Education, Teaching, Slow learners, Learning, Improving.

1. Introduction

Education is one of the many sectors that artificial intelligence (AI) is revolutionizing. This technology may soon transform how instructors instruct young people. In fact, it's already happening. Schools all across the globe are adopting AI programmes into their curricula to help improve teaching and learning, even if they are not yet at the level of global acceptance that will be attained in decades [1]. Strong technologies like artificial intelligence (AI) could be applied to enhance current educational systems. There have long been barriers to admission when it comes to education. All students have difficulty keeping up with the demands of a traditional educational system, and teachers have historically been overworked.

Accessibility and time management are already two areas where digitalization has benefited education. The reach of AI will, however, increase as it develops and grows. By 2025, the market for AI in education is expected to grow to \$5.80 billion, as per Market Research Engine.

A rising range of interactive education technologies were becoming more and more popular. While student utilize tablets instead textbooks, teacher use a variety of learning platforms including Moodle, Power School, Edmodo, and Google Classroom. Online learning is possible through Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs), like coursera.com. The rise in MOOC enrollment indicates that society is supporting online and distance learning. Additionally, some of the courses may give students the chance to graduate with a real diploma from a renowned university. The development of “artificial intelligence (AI), augmented reality (AR), virtual reality (VR)”, and its educational applications were all seen at the same time [2,3]. To understand particularly abstract subjects, there are several augmented reality (AR) education apps available.

Although every student's learning style is unique, generally they are divided into three categories based on learning: Passive learners, Slow learners, Quick Learners. For each of these three groups of learners, there are specific ways that AI as a learning tool can be used to achieve the desired learning results, as described in table 1. This study's main goal is to determine how artificial intelligence affects teaching for slow learners.

Table 1. Various types of learners and how AI impact their learning

Sl.no	Learner Type	Impact of AI
1.	Rapid Learners	For this group of learners who absorb the most information in the shortest period of time, AI, which attempts to add more to what is customary, acts like a magic wand. Contrary to fears that technology will have a negative impact on these children, it can really help them learn a lot. They do not had to compete with their subpar classmates or undergo evaluations to advance levels in an AI learning environment.
2.	Slow Learners	The slow learners are the patient group, as opposed to the rapid learners. They need time to understand, remember, and repeat their lesson. This group struggles the hardest and does the least well in a classroom setting. This group of pupils frequently loses motivation and has little possibility of climbing the learning curve, defying the adage "Slow and steady wins the race." Slow learning, on the other hand, is a continual process even though it moves slowly. So, by assisting these children in tutoring themselves within the AI environment, well-designed AI programmes may do wonders for them.
3.	Passive learners	This group of learners acquires knowledge passively from a teacher or source of information of their choice and internalizes it without knowing feedback or engagement by the instructor. Learning is passive in classroom settings when there is little or no contact between the teacher and the students. In some knowledge areas where argumentative examination of issues or circumstances is not necessary, passive learning is particularly successful. It may be difficult to develop AI modules for passive learners since there is little to no contact between the instructor and the student, making it impossible for programmer to assess if her AI module had been successful in promoting learning [4].

2. Literature survey

For thoroughly abstracting how AI approaches solve instructional challenges and learning in education, Ouyang et al. suggested AIED paradigms. To create AI tools for teaching, Chung et al. objectively measure happiness and despair. Xiao et al. suggested a method for building an AI-based tailored training model. Lin et al. sought to explore structure of student's AI learning motivation and look into any potential gender inequalities.

To assess the effects of AI on sustainable development, concentrating on creation of Sustainable Development Goals, Goralski et al. merged corporate strategy and public policy views. New directions and difficulties facing use of big data and AI in education research, business, and policy making were highlighted in Luan et al.. Renz et al. concentrated on Educational Technology businesses and the factors that now influence data-based instruction and learning routes[27][29][30].

The present status of medical education was discussed, the framework to expanding curriculum to include AI was proposed by Paranjape et al.. Through a systematic study, Zawacki-Richter et al., gave an overview of the literature on AI application in higher education. Chen et al., made a contribution to AIED by making it easier for academics and teachers to comprehend the current state and development of publications and grants associated with AIED.

The interaction of AI, computational thinking (CT), mathematics education (ME) for young children was investigated by Gadanidis et al.. Ee et al. looked into how mathematics education is changing as the result of paradigm shift in education and how AI is developing in response to the advancement of communication and information technologies. In order to comprehend important ideas in AI research from the standpoint of education, Goksel et al. employed social network analysis (SNA)[24][25].

As per a study of AI systems in higher education by Ocaña-Fernández et al., smart tutors already had provided praise and encouragement help and support on a variety of subjects with one's sensible

origins, such as mentoring in chemistry, genetics, programming, computing, medical diagnosis, circuits, and geography, and they'd be popular tools for enhancing web learning in the future. A few methods for instruction and feedback, including Samarakou et al. and Saplacan et al., are also utilized for assessment[23][28].

Intelligent Tutoring System (ITS) and Computer-Based Instruction (CBI) are two different kinds of computer tutors, according to VanLehn et al.. In the first kind of tutoring, the student merely needs to compose a response; the professor will subsequently provide comments. Students can input data for each stage of process using ITS just as if they are working on issue on the paper. Based on all of the students' responses, the system will provide feedback. As a result, the primary distinction between those two systems is that ITS has the potential to engage students at the step-level rather than only providing feedback once a job has been completed by Ma W. et al..

There are a variety of conceptual frameworks and techniques for ITS, according to Sabo et al.. For instance, Carnegie Learning's Adaptive Control of Thought-Rational (ACT-R) tutors are based on the examination of subject area production norms and their major goal is to replicate human cognition. Knowledge space theory (KST), a feature of ALEKS, attempts to imitate the capacity of an experienced instructor to evaluate a student's knowledge status. Babitha et al., gave an overview how AI helps in conducting online exam. AI methods not just provided in education, it gave good results in other sectors like health [22], plant disease detection [20] and many more.

3. Main challenges of using AI in education

Transparency and ethics

While using AI, some sociological and ethical considerations need to be taken into account. What is currently impossible may become achievable tomorrow as technology develops at a dizzying speed.

Information security and privacy are the first topics that come up in any discussion about digital ethics. The issue is protecting individual privacy preferences and individually identifiable information when using personal data. Data collection and use must be supported by clear, informed consent, transparency, and fairness.

Hefty delivery cost

The hardest parts of using AI in education are financial planning and strategy. Budgeting is really challenging almost often. The amount of electricity needed would increase, for example, if robot assistants were permitted in every classroom. As a result, nations would have had to spend a substantial amount of money to fulfil their responsibilities. Power is not actually a natural resource, which is another disadvantage. One must first be aware of the intelligence learning approaches that may be used and how they can benefit students if you want to reduce this gap.

4. Teaching slow learners: The impact of artificial intelligence technologies

Because they are afraid of the outcomes, slow learners frequently refuse to take standard test series. These children would like taking such exams repeatedly if they were in a setting with a self-assessing AI suite because they can genuinely see their development on each test without having it evaluated by a human teacher. A robot companion that is programmed to follow the children's rate of learning would make learning the basics of physics and other physical sciences much simpler.

The use of information generators, AI predictions, inferences based on user history, regional interests of the academics, and interactions with them all help slow learners create a better knowledge base and catch up to their contemporaries. In an AI learning environment, young children may learn via trial and error without fear of harm.

AI robots can also teach slow learners to adjust to changes in their environment because slow learners typically preserve exclusionary features such being introverted, unapproachable, and closed to everyone. Parents and instructors may better track these children's progress by putting them through specifically designed AI-based learning modules, which allows them to foster an atmosphere that is both empowering and positive for the children. These children may learn and develop various abilities by using social media in a constructive way because AI is ingrained in every social media site.

For slow learners, it is always challenging to solve issues of a complex and varied nature, and the fundamental tenet of AI is the ability to solve difficulties. Thus, the match. Slow learners won't feel as though they are less effective or slower at solving problems than others in a well-tailored AI learning environment. In reality, when individuals progress from being slow learners, the issue of delayed fact awareness is eventually resolved. Different ways, that AI impacts slow learners is shown in figure 1.

4.1 Global access Education

Students/slow learners may now learn anyplace, at any moment, thanks to artificial education. This implies that students who may skip class due to personal or medical reasons can simply catch up on their coursework using computerized education programmes. Additionally, students may study from anywhere in the globe, making higher education accessible and inexpensive for students in rural areas and those from low-income backgrounds.

With the aid of AI, children may learn more outside of the classroom and enter the classroom with a foundational set of skills that teachers can expand upon. Artificial education is levelling the playing field for students worldwide and providing equal opportunity to those who lack access to high-quality education.

Figure 1. Different ways, that AI helps teaching slow learners

4.2 Teachers can access additional data

When evaluating student achievement in the classroom, the data seldom lies. Teachers now have greater access than ever before to a range of data that can help them pinpoint student weaknesses thanks to the development of artificial intelligence. This information could highlight topic areas or learning styles where the majority of students are having difficulty. Additionally, it offers teachers a clearer picture of how learning-disabilities pupils are actually faring in comparison to their peers.

4.3 AI may be used by students to provide accurate feedback

The inability to give consistent feedback while educating kids with learning disabilities is one of the most significant problems. It might be difficult to take your time in a large classroom in order to assist a few students. Students can now get more trustworthy feedback that is directly tied to their own performance thanks to the fast emerging field of artificial intelligence. Students may progress through the course at their own pace if required, and the system won't let them continue on until they've proven that they understand a topic.

4.4 Personalized and Customized learning

It can occasionally be difficult to ensure that the child catches up when they don't comprehend the subject taught in the class. Children get lost in the crowd in our big classrooms. Given their distance from their own elementary school years, parents may find it challenging to educate their young children the new standards required of them.

With personalized and customized coaching from experts and more experienced peers, artificial intelligence may bridge the gap. Without surrendering their grades and accomplishments, students can avoid the shame and embarrassment of excessively soliciting help in front of their peers. These digital services make tutoring more available and cheap than ever before.

4.5 Educators can recognize learning problems of student with the use of AI

Finding these difficulties in a student is the first step in understanding how to work with them. Not all of the testing techniques used today are very good at detecting learning disorders. To assist instructors in giving more accurate exams that could reveal some of these frequently undetected problems, new artificial intelligence technologies are being created. Educators can use the resources for learning disabilities once they have been correctly diagnosed.

4.6 Artificial intelligence can deliver information in a clear manner

Reading more complex texts might be challenging for slow learners. They can have trouble understanding complicated sentence patterns or having trouble understanding common idioms used in the text itself. Artificial intelligence is being developed by scientists and academics to transform these difficult texts into resources that are easier to grasp. They could formulate a clearer statement or swap out witty expressions for more straightforward ones. It ought to be a fantastic approach for kids with learning difficulties to connect with and interact with the subject matter.

4.7 Computer determines the ideal tempo

There is no such thing as a one-size-fits-all method of imparting a lesson, as trained educators have long realized. Setting the ideal speed while including every conceivable learning type into each class is all but impossible. Slow learners must not fall behind while fast learners must maintain their interest.

The ideal speed is a difficult notion to grasp as the number of pupils rises. These days, artificial intelligence may assist in determining the ideal speed for each learners.

5. Conclusion

Even though they can seem like futuristic innovations, artificial intelligence (AI) and education are now present in our daily lives and in schools. By applying AI in education, we can make both students' and teachers' life easier. AI-based education personalizes learning and enables all students to receive a top-notch education. Although each student has a different learning style, they may typically be categorized into three groups depending on how quickly they pick things up: passive learners, slow learners, and quick learners. We did an survey, on how artificial intelligence influences teaching to slow learners and also provided different ways to teach slow learners using AI methods.

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